

THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF CONTINUOUS CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED COPPER MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The paper deals with thermal conductivity of the continuous carbon fibre reinforced - copper matrix composite that can be applied in the field of electric and electronic industry as a heat sink material. The copper matrix - carbon fibre composite with different fibre orientation and fibre content was produced by diffusion bonding of copper-coated carbon fibres. Laser flash technique was used for thermal conductivity characterisation in direction parallel and transverse to fibre orientation. The results revealed decreasing thermal conductivity as the volume content of fibre increased and independence of through thickness conductivity on fibre orientation. Achieved results were compared with the materials that are currently used as heat sinks and possibility of the copper-based composite application was analysed.

KEYWORDS: thermal conductivity, copper matrix, carbon fibre, metal matrix composite, heat sink, thermal management, heat dissipation

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced - copper matrix composite (Cu-C_f MMC) offer thermomechanical properties (TMP) which are now required in electronic and electric industry. Their advantages are low density, very good thermal conductivity and tailorable coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE). These properties are important in the applications where especially thermal conductivity plays large role to solve the problems of heat dissipation due to the usage of increasingly powerful electronic components. In devices, where high density mounting technology is applied thermal management is crucial for the reliability and long life performance. Heat produced by the integrated circuits and by other electronic modules can be removed by using of a new generation of heat sink material. The Cu-C_f MMC is a candidate for the application, e.g. packaging for high voltage chips, cooling plates for microwaves and heat sinks, which all serve for heat dissipation [1]. Except for good thermal conductivity, it should have the CTE to match those of electronic materials. The composite should fulfil several requirements e.g. thermal conductivity 200 - 300 W/m.K, the CTE matching the substrate material 5 - 8 ppm/ K, good joinability, structural stability during thermal cycling within a defined temperature range [2].

Traditional materials used in this field such as Cu, Al, Cu-Invar and Cu-Mo-Cu laminates, Invar and Kovar Ni-Fe alloys as well as Cu-Mo and Cu-W blends have some limitations such as high density

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(Mo, Cu) and limited thermal conductivity (Invar, Kovar).

Metal matrix composites reinforced with carbon fibres consist of two components with different thermal properties. While copper is one of the best conductors, carbon fibres may or may not be good conductors. Some fibres have conductivity in axial direction higher than that of copper (PITCH - Thornel K 1100) and other ones behave like poor conductors (PAN Torayca T-300). It is assumed that in transverse direction conductivity of carbon fibres is low and approaches zero. Thermal conductivity of the composite depends on volume fraction, orientation, type and length of carbon fibres and properties of the matrix. Anisotropic properties of carbon fibres influence also thermal conductivity of the composite in direction along fibres and transversely to it. For unidirectional composites usage of high conductive fibres may help to improve overall thermal conductivity in fibre direction and the in-plane conductivity of cross-ply and woven composites. However, using the high performance fibres can not increase transverse conductivity owing to their low transverse properties.

MATERIAL PROCESSING

The Cu-C_f MMC was prepared from copper coated carbon fibres (Torayca T-300) with 3000 filaments in one tow. The fibres have been coated continuously in the laboratory line in a semi-automated regime. A thickness of copper coating was in the range 1-2 μm. The layer was smooth, continuous and without gaps [3]. Copper-coated carbon fibres with different copper thicknesses could provide 40, 50 and 60 vol. % of fibre in the composite. The fibre bundles were wound in one layer onto a steel plate at a precise spacing. After winding two monolayers at both sides of the plate were diffusion bonded at 100 MPa and 873 K (600 °C) in vacuum for 15 minutes. In this way, unidirectional monolayers with a thickness of about 0,25 mm were produced.

In order to analyse thermophysical properties of the composite several types of fibre orientations have been designed. The unidirectional composites served for analysis in two basic directions - parallel and transverse to fibres, in which properties are very anisotropic. To have isotropic/homogenous properties at least in two directions the cross-ply, spiral and plain weave pattern of fibre orientation was utilised.

The monolayers were then laid up as n-ply (n = 14-50) and hot pressed to the unidirectional or cross-ply plates (Fig.1a). The unidirectional samples contained 40, 50 and 60 % C_f. The cross-ply composite was produced of monolayers containing 60 vol. % C_f. Some samples have been prepared with copper foils (0,06 mm thick) which were placed in-between the monolayers. Such samples contained 50 vol. % C_f. The even number of layers assured quasi-isotropic properties within the plane of fibres and

Fig. 1: Illustration of carbon fibre arrangement in different samples of the copper - carbon fibre composite.

therefore such lay ups were preferable. Considering bending moments, odd number of layers allows a symmetric stacking with respect to a central plane (Fig.1b). Woven samples were prepared in a different way. From copper-coated carbon fibre tows, a 0°/90° plain weave fabric - a tape - have been

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produced. The tapes were stacked to a required thickness and then diffusion bonded to plate samples (Fig.1d). Fibre volume fraction in the woven composite was 40 vol. %. Diffusion bonding parameters are presented in literature [4].

Spiral samples in a shape of a disc have been prepared by winding of copper-coated carbon fibre tows containing 57 vol. % C_f on a steel mandrel with a diameter 0.5 mm. After winding the mandrel was removed and wound fibres were hot pressed under vacuum at 850 °C and 34 MPa. The disc samples had 3 mm in the thickness and 12 mm in the diameter (Fig.1c).

MATERIAL CHARACTERISATION

Methods that are used for characterisation of thermal transport properties of matter are divided in two basic groups: steady-state methods and transient methods. Under steady-state conditions, only one parameter - thermal conductivity k ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$) that is measured directly, is sufficient. At present transient methods are most frequently used for stating thermal conductivity of composites. Mathematical base for the measurement is Eqn 1, which is valid for isotropic solids where thermal conductivity is independent on both the temperature T and the position in the orthogonal system defined by axis x, y, z :

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{k}{c \cdot \rho} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

where symbol ρ stands for density of the sample. Thermal diffusivity a , determines how quickly heat propagates through a material during a transient stage. By measuring of a one can calculate thermal conductivity from Eqn 2.

$$\frac{k}{c \cdot \rho} = a \quad (2)$$

Thermal diffusivity was measured by using of a dynamic laser-flash method where laser beam supplied a flash of energy to the front face of a thin disc. A time interval of the flash was short compared with the time required for the resulting transient flow of heat to propagate through the sample. Main parameters of the test method were:

- as heat source served Nd-glass laser, with a pulse width 0.5 ms.
- heat pulse applied to a front face of the sample had energy ca.1 J.cm.⁻²
- the diameter of the laser beam at the sample was 12 mm
- in order to have uniform emissivity with a value near unity the samples were coated with carbon
- the transient rear face temperature response was measured by an IR-detector, which viewed an area of about 6 x 6 mm
- ambient temperature was measured also by Pt -10 Rh Pt thermocouple

Temperature as a function of time at the rear face of the disc was automatically recorded. The thermal diffusivity was given from the thickness of the sample, l , and specific time, $t_{1/2}$, at which the back-face reaches half its maximum value according to the formula in the temperature interval from RT to 300 °C:

$$a = \frac{0.139 \cdot l^2}{t_{1/2}} \quad (3)$$

Thermal conductivity of samples was then calculated from the Eqn. 2. Samples had the shape of a disc with dimensions $\varnothing 10$ mm x 3 mm. Parallel surfaces of samples had to be machined with tolerance $\pm 0,01$ mm. The density of all samples (ρ^s) was measured by the Archimedes method. Specific heat is an

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important parameter for thermal conductivity calculation. For the composite specific heat (c^c) can be stated from the Eqn 4 that represents the rule of mixtures (ROM), from properties of constituents [5],

$$c^c = \frac{1}{\rho^c} \cdot (V^f \cdot \rho^f \cdot c_p^f + V^m \cdot \rho^m \cdot c_p^m) \quad (4)$$

where V is volume fraction of constituents and for properties of the fibre and the matrix stands superscript f and m , respectively and density of the composite (ρ^c) can be calculated

$$\rho^c = V^f \cdot \rho^f + V^m \cdot \rho^m \quad (5)$$

It is useful to verify the rule of mixtures by measurements. Specific heat was measured by Differential Scanning Calorimetry between room temperature and 300 °C in inert gas atmosphere by using of a Perkin Elmer DSCII drop calorimeter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Specific heat

Measurements revealed that specific heat of the Cu-C_f MMC increased with increasing both temperature and fibre content. Specific heat can be also obtained from the rule of mixture (ROM). For confirming if the ROM (Eqn 4) can give reasonable values that are suitable for thermal conductivity calculation, the theoretical curves were compared with measured values (Fig.2). Comparison was made for two temperatures 50 and 250 °C.

Fig.2: Measured specific heat compared with calculated values by rule of mixtures. Comparison made for temperature 50 °C (dashed line and full squares) and for 250 °C (full line and triangles).

Theoretical curves were obtained from data of copper and carbon fibres at 50 and 250 °C published in [6, 7]. In Fig.2 is confirmed that measured values are in reasonable agreement with ROM that can be used for obtaining of specific heat values needed for thermal conductivity calculations.

Thermal conductivity

Thermal diffusivity of unidirectional samples was measured in two principal directions – longitudinal (L) and transverse (T) to fibre orientation. Thermal conductivity was calculated from eq.2. In Fig.3 is visible that transverse conductivity is much lower than the axial one and the difference was more than 100 % between the samples containing the same fibre fraction. Thermal conductivity of the composite did not change with increasing temperature. Only transverse conductivity of the sample containing 40 % C_f revealed increasing trend. The highest axial and transverse conductivity achieved the unidirectional composite containing 40 vol. % C_f (at 100 °C : $k_L^c = 225$ W/m.K and $k_T^c = 120$ W/m.K). It decreased with increasing fibre content owing to very low conductivity of T-300 carbon fibres. One may assume that low conductive fibres can not transfer heat, which is then transferred preferably by

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copper. In comparison to longitudinal direction, lower transverse conductivity of the composite might be attributed to a presence of the copper network that is not so good as in axial direction.

Other important phenomenon can be found in Fig.3. Thermal conductivity of Oxygen Free High Conductivity (OFHC) copper decreased with increasing temperature. This is normal behavior of homogenous materials. Nevertheless, conductivity of the composite increased slightly with increasing temperature. According to the observation, it can be presumed that if heat were transferred only through the copper matrix, the conductivity of the composite should have decreased with rising temperature. Because it was not so probably one part of heat has been transferred also through fibres. Then fibre-matrix interface and contact conduction could play a certain role in transportation phenomena preferably at higher temperature.

Fig. 3: Comparison of both longitudinal (dashed line) and transverse (full line) thermal conductivity of the unidirectional composite. Samples containing 60, 50 and 40 % of fibres are marked by the circles, triangles and crosses, respectively.

Interface can be described as a contact of two surfaces where heat transfer is carried out by following mechanisms: heat conduction, heat convection and radiation. Radiation plays an important role at temperatures higher than 600 °C and need not to be considered here. With increasing temperature, thermal contact conductance rapidly increases at normal pressure in gas atmosphere [8]. Although both measurements and production were performed in vacuum, some gas, e.g.CO, might be present inside the sample at the interface. It could be generated from the reaction of oxygen (from Cu_2O) and graphite [9]. According to that deduction, at low temperature the interface may have higher thermal resistance. At higher temperature, the resistance is lower and increasing heat transfer through fibres can compensate decreasing conductivity of copper. This may explain the fact that measured thermal conductivity of the composite did not decrease with increasing temperature.

Thermal conductivity of cross-plyed samples was measured in longitudinal (in-plane) and transverse directions to fibre orientation (Fig.4). The sample with added copper foils achieved at 100 °C higher in-plane thermal conductivity $k_{in-plane}^c$ (Cu foils) = 150 W/m.K than the one without copper foils $k_{in-plane}^c$ (no foils) = 115 W/m.K. The sample with Cu foils showed higher conductivity by ca. 22 % but difference between the samples in fibre content was 9 %. Transverse conductivity of the sample with copper foils (containing 50 % C_f) was much lower and can be compared with transverse conductivity of the unidirectional material containing 60 vol. % C_f . The main role of the copper foils was to help the composite to withstand thermal cycling without large damage (e.g. fewer cracks) [10].

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Fig. 4: In-plane thermal conductivity of the cross-ply composite with and without Cu foils and transverse conductivity of the sample with Cu foils.

Thermal conductivity of composites with spiral fibre orientation

Conductivity of the composite with spiral orientation of fibres (disc - 57 % C_f) was measured only in direction parallel to the disc axis - transversally to fibres. It is compared with transverse conductivity of the unidirectional composite containing similar (60 % C_f) fibre content in Fig.5.

Fig. 5: Transverse thermal conductivity of the disc (line with full circles) compared with transverse conductivity of the unidirectional composite (triangles).

Thermal conductivity of woven composites

The sample containing 40 vol. % of carbon fibres has been measured. The in-plane thermal conductivity of the composite was higher $k_{in-plane}^c(100^\circ\text{C}) = 157 \text{ W/m.K}$ than transverse conductivity $k_T^c(100^\circ\text{C}) = 120 \text{ W/m.K}$. Difference between these two directions (ca. 22 %) did not change in temperature range in which measurement was performed (Fig.6).

Fig. 6: Comparison of transverse and in-plane thermal conductivity of the woven material containing 40 % of fibres.

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From the above results follows that in-plane conductivity of analysed Cu-C_f composites depends on fibre fraction in direction of measurement. The cross-ply and woven samples containing 49 and 40 % C_f, respectively fulfilled requirements (see Table 1).

Transverse conductivity of the Cu-C_f composite was low. In Fig.7 are compared samples having different fibre orientation and very similar fibre content. Unidirectional and woven samples (40 % C_f) have nearly the same transverse conductivity. Other samples (unidirectional and spiral with 60 and 56 % C_f) have conductivities also in a close range. From the results follows that transverse conductivity did not depend on fibre orientation. All samples should have had low or zero porosity that was confirmed in [11] according to mathematical predictions for continuously reinforced composites with different fibre orientation. Generally, transverse conductivity of the Cu-C_f MMC measured in this work and published by other authors was much lower than expected one. In the literature [12] the cross-ply Cu-C_f MMC containing 43 vol. % high conductive PITCH fibres (Thornel K-1100) exhibited through-plane conductivity only 32.4 W/m.K. Samples presented in the paper (low conductive PAN T-300 fibre), both cross-ply and woven composites containing 50 and 40 % C_f, exhibited in transverse direction 54 and 120 W/m.K, respectively. From the example is seen that high conductive fibres did not have positive effect to transverse conductivity.

Fig.7 : Comparison of transverse thermal conductivity of Cu-C_f composites having different fibre orientation. Compared are materials with similar fibre content.

In-plane thermal conductivity and density of materials currently used as heat sinks are compared with both cross-ply and woven Cu-C_f MMC in Fig.8. Unidirectional composites are not involved to the comparison because their properties are anisotropic. Presented are cross-ply and woven samples of suitable fibre content that have the mean CTE (between RT and 50 °C) comparable with the one of currently used heat sink materials ($\bar{\alpha} = 8-9$ ppm/K).

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Fig. 8: Comparison of physical properties of current heat sink materials with that of cross-ply and woven Cu-C_f MMCs. In-plane thermal **conductivity** is represented by **columns** and density is described by the line with triangles.

From Fig.8 one can see that "in-plane" thermal conductivity of the Cu-C_f MMC will of course never meet the one of diamond or BN, which also have low density. Other light materials such as AlN, Al-SiC and Al-alloys have comparable thermal conductivity and the first two materials have low the CTE and weight. Higher conductivity can achieve pure metals and some blends (e.g. 20 Cu - 80 W, 20 Cu-80 Mo), which on the other hand can not compete in the field of weight and thermal expansion. Thermal conductivity of the Cu-C_f MMC measured along fibres could be improved if high conductive fibres are used. Their advantage is also the lower CTE. Such a composite would contain less high conductive fibres but its CTE would be at the same level as those of the composite containing T-300 fibres. In this case, thermal conductivity both in-plane and transverse, would increase also due to higher copper content. Disadvantage of high conductive fibres is higher price and more difficult continuous copper coating.

Transverse thermal conductivity is not satisfying and does not depend on fibre orientation. It should be improved in the future in order to assure the composite's competitiveness. Because carbon fibres are not very good conductors in transverse direction one of the possible route is to increase the overall copper content in the composite and producing the interconnected copper network.

But, the relatively low price of continuous copper coating of high strength carbon fibres like T-300 offers the possibility to produce the Cu-C_f MMC heat sink at reasonable cost with good thermophysical properties e.g. low thermal expansion and relatively high thermal conductivity. The continuous copper coating of carbon fibres is the essential factor of this production route and can be considered as a relatively cheap process, which can be run totally automated.

CONCLUSION

Thermal conductivity of the continuous carbon fibre - copper matrix composite was measured by the laser flash method. Unidirectional, cross-ply and woven samples revealed in direction along fibres good thermal conductivity ($k_{in-plane}^c \approx 150$ W/m.K) and the transverse of conductivity of the composite was low ($k^c \approx 50$ W/m.K). From the measurements followed that conductivity decreased with increasing fibre content. In-plane conductivity of cross-ply samples with Cu foils and woven samples could fulfil requirements stated by the industry. Transverse conductivity was lower and did not depend on fibre orientation confirming zero porosity in the composite. Properties of the Cu-C_f MMC have been compared with those of current heat sink materials. While its in-plane conductivity is at the same or higher level in transverse direction conductivity is low. It should be improved by preparing the composite with built-in Cu bridges that would help to transfer heat through the thickness of the plate material.

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